

MORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES OF THE TYMUS OF STILLBORN INFANTS

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Abstract: The thymus of infants confirmed in the autopsy materials of a stillborn fetus with infection in the mother was studied. The average weight of the thymus of babies in this group is 7.21 ± 1.31 g, and the thymus of healthy babies of the same period is 9.85 ± 2.17 g. The average thymus weight was found to be 28.65% smaller than the norm. In the 36-39 weeks of intrauterine development of the fetus, the effect of secondary infections developed in the mother was not strongly manifested in the development of the thymus, the main changes were secondary changes in the morphofunctional areas of the salivary gland, the formation of a large number of Gassal bodies, signs of fullness in the veins were determined.

Key words: thymus, morphology, involution, immunodeficiency, necrosis.

Relevance of the problem: According to newborns in the world, the average is 4-5 per 1000 births in the USA and Europe. The world's five highest rates are Turkmenistan 45, Tajikistan 33, Azerbaijan 21, Kyrgyzstan 17 and Uzbekistan 16 cases per 1000 births. This indicates that full screening of extragenital diseases during intrauterine development or examinations that should be done during pregnancy have not been fully implemented. In perinatal pathologies, antenatal death mainly develops together with infectious and non-infectious etiological processes and manifests itself in the form of fetal immaturity, asphyxia, birth trauma, pneumopathies, perinatal blood circulation disorders in the brain, and hemorrhagic disease of newborns.

The purpose of the study is to study the pathomorphological features of the thymus tissue of stillborn babies.

Result and discussion: In our study, 36-39-week-old babies who died from various infectious factors and were stillborn were taken. According to the organometric parameters of the thymus according to the gestational period, morphologically the following were determined. It was found that the external

fibrous capsule has grown into the cortex in a trabecular form, the septal barriers are sharply expanded, and there are many rough structures with fibroblasts and collagen fibers. At the same time, the fullness of trabecular blood vessels, the development of interstitial tumors formed in the perivascular area, and in many cases, the presence of foci of disorganization in the fibrous structures were determined.

It was characterized by an abundance of thymocytes with dark hyperchromic nuclei with foci of small-sized lymphocytes in the cortex. A large accumulation of macrophages in the cortex, fragments of apoptized lymphocytes in the cytoplasm are detected. Reticulo-epithelial cells are located along the perimeter of the lobes, and small lymphocyte foci clusters are identified around their walls. In the interval, it was found that reticulocytes and sparse fibers located in different directions formed the basis of the swollen thymic stroma, and nurse cells were located along the perimeter of the cortical layer, and a small number of small lymphocytes were found around it. These identified signs mean that the thymus has undergone an accidental transformation from a clinical and morphological point of view, and it confirms the occurrence of primary cellular immunodeficiency due to the development of intrauterine infection in stillborn babies at 36-39 weeks. Exactly, at 36-39 weeks, the size of the thymus is reduced by 28.6% compared to the control group, which is explained by the fact that it developed in parallel with the enlargement of the adrenal gland.

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